

REVIEW ON THE PLANTS USED FOR THE NEPHROPROTECTIVE ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

Nephrotoxicity is a common complication caused by the drugs, toxins and metabolic disorders leading to serious kidney damage. Many of the medicinal plants have emerged as an effective nephroprotective agent due to their rich phytochemical constituents such as flavonoids, phenolics, tannins and alkaloids. This plants summaries several of the plants used for the kidney protective activity. This plant highlights the various antioxidant, Anti inflammatory and detoxifying mechanism of several of the plants overall plants based therapies show significant potential in preventing renal injury but further standardize reaserch and clinical validation is need.

KEYWORDS: Nephroprotection, kidney damage, Traditional medicines.

INTRODUCTION

Kidney is the main important organ in the human body. It plays the vital role in maintaining the homeostasis of the human body. It helps in maintain the electrolyte balance, excreting metabolic waste and controlling human BP. Kidneys are highly sensitive to the damage caused by the nephrotoxic drugs. Drug induce nephrotoxicity from the agents such cisplatin, Gentamycin, paracetamol and is one of the most common leading problem often leading to the Acute and Chronic kidney injury. Despite significant advancement in modern therapeutics, current treatment options remain limited, expensive and often associated with the adverse effects Many of the medicinal plants found in india have been traditionally used across various cultures for the kidney related disorders. Now a days this are gaining

scientific attention due to their potential nephroprotective activity. Their nephroprotective activity is attributed to the various of the bioactive component like flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, terpenoids and glycosides. This all have a strong antioxidant, anti- inflammatory, anti-apoptotic and free radical scavenging activities.

This review aims to compile and critically analyse the available literature on medicinal plants with the nephroprotective activity focusing on their ethnomedicinal significance, phytochemical profiles and mechanism of action.

Understanding this natural therapeutics options may contribute to the development of the safer, and effective intervention for renal protection^[1,2,3,21,10,12 14 ,15]

Sr. No	Plant name	Family	Parts used	Types of extract/ Active phytoconstituents	Mechanism of action	Referance
1	Eurycoma longifolia	Simaroubaceae	Root	Aqueous root extrat	It will enhances antioxidant enzyme , improve kidneys biomarker and will reduce the tissue injury caused by NSAID	[20] [1]
2	Arbutus pavarii	Ericaceae	Leaves	Phenolic rich extract containing gallic acid,epicatechin and quercetin	It will exhibit strong bacteriostatic and bacteriocidal action against the staphylococcus aureus which will prevent against antibiotic associated renal stress	[3]
3	Punica grantum	Lythraceae	Fruit peel	Ethanolic extract rich in polyphenol	It will protect the renal tissue by controlling ROS generation,reducing the oxidative injury and suppressing inflammatory mediators	[4] [5]
4	Theobroma cacao	Malvaceae	Seeds(cocoa powder)	Hydroalcoholic extract of natural forastero cocoa	It will helps regulate the glucose level by lowering metabolic burden on kidney	[6]
5	Coffea arabica	Rubiaceae	Coffee pulp	Aq. Pulp extract	It will boost the catalase activity and strengthen antioxidant defence	[7]
6	Eysenhardtia polystachya	Fabaceae	Bark	Methanolic bark extract	Decrease oxidative stress and protect against diabetes related renal	[8]

					structural and functional abnormalities	
7	Hibiscus sabdariffa	Malvaceae	Calyx	Aqueous calyx extract	Enhance enzymatic and non enzymatic antioxidant system preventing metabolic syndrome induce renal oxidative stress	[9]
8	Hibiscus sabdariffa	Malvaceae	Calyx	Calyx powder and aqueous extract containing hibiscus acid anthocyanin	Regulate blood pressure and stabilize renal hemodynamic in hypertensive patients	[8] [9]
9	Cichorium intybus	Asteraceae	Whole plant	Aq extract rich in naphthofurane p-methoxycinnamate	Enhances the systolic heart function and improves renal perfusion helping prevent pre-renal and the post renal complications associated with high blood pressure induced renal strain	[10]
10	Gardenia jasminoides	Rubiaceae	Fruits	Geniposide	It shows strong antioxidant activity decrease cardiac and liver injury biomarkers during MI	[11]

Nephroprotective Plants used as Traditional Medicine.

Sr. No	Plant name	Family	Parts used	Types of extract/ Active phytoconstituents	Mechanism of action	Reference
11	Curcuma longa	Zingiberaceae	Rhizomes	Curcumin	It reduces ROS , inflammation and muscle breakdowns markers in rhabdomyolysis, helping prevent acute tubular damage	[12] [13]
12	Passiflora spp	Passifloraceae	Fruit peel	Methanolic peel extract containing gallic acid ,ellagic acid kaemferol quercetin	Maintains normal urea and creatinine level, prevents paracetamol induced nephrotoxicity	[14]
13	Euphorbia paralias	Euphorbiaceae	Aerial parts	Methanolic extract	Reduces elevated urea creatinine and kidney tissue damage	[15]
14	Pistacia atlantica	Anacardiaceae	Leaves	Hydro alcoholic extract	It lower harmful renal biomarkers and protects architecture in gentamicin induce nephrotoxicity	[16]

15	<i>Costus afer</i>	Costaceae	Leaves	Aqueous leaf extract	It reduces serum potassium and BUN level and protects against cyclosporine induced nephrotoxicity by lowering oxidative stress and improving renal function	[17]
16	<i>Tinospora crispa</i>	Menispermaceae	Steam	Genkwanin extract	It increases [SOD] activity ,enhances antioxidant defence. Thus preventing oxidative stress induce renal damage	[22]
17	<i>Cirsium vulgare</i>	Asteraceae	Whole plant extract	Lupeol acetate	Prevent depletion of liver glycogen, reduces oxidative damage and provide anti-inflammatory protection	[23]
18	<i>Suaeda vermiculata</i>	Amaranthaceae	Leaves and aerial part	Ethanollic extract containing flavonoids	It will decrease AST and ALT level of blood .	[24]
18	<i>Descurainia sophia</i>	Brassicaceae	Seeds	Dried seed ethyl acetate extract	It will reduce inflammation , swelling and necrosis in NSAID induced hepatic injury	[25]
19	<i>Vaccinium spp</i> [Cranberry]	Ericaceae	Fruit	Natural cranberry extract	Prevents E.coli adhesion to urothelium I	[27] [28]
20	<i>Descurainia sophia</i>	Brassicaceae	Seeds	Aqueous extract	Will decrease the calcium oxalate deposition and reduces renal tissue damage in urolithiasis	[29]
21	<i>Equisetum arvense</i>	Equisetaceae	steam	Alcoholic extract	It increase the urinary flow and protects against urinary flow and protects against urinary retention	[30]

CONCLUSION

This paper shows the nephroprotective plants which are having valuable therapeutic benefits capable of modulating key pathological pathway involved in renal injury, including the oxidative stress, inflammation and mitochondrial dysfunction. The phytochemicals present in these plants are flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, phenolics and glycosides; they will contribute significantly to restoring renal biomarkers.

The current body of evidence is predominantly preclinical with wide variety in plant parts used, extraction technique, phytochemical standardization.

Overall nephroprotective plants hold significant translational potential but their integration into evidence based therapy requires integration into evidence based therapy requires rigorous scientific validation.^[1, 2, 3, 4, 21, 25]

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